

e-ISSN: 2584-2404

Volume 09 Issue 01 Jan-Apr
2026

***Corresponding Author:-
Sharanagouda,**

*Student, Department of
Electrical & Electronics, PDA
College of Engineering,
Kalaburagi, India*

Submission Date: Dec 03,
2025

Copyright Received Date:
Dec 06, 2025

Fault Detection In 3-Phase under Ground System Using Aurdino

***Prof. Megha Upase¹, Prajwal², Sharanagouda^{3*},
Sudeep⁴, Venkatesh⁵***

*¹Assistant Professor, Department of Electrical & Electronics,
PDA College of Engineering, Kalaburagi, India*

*^{2,3,4,5}Student, Department of Electrical & Electronics, PDA
College of Engineering, Kalaburagi, India*

ABSTRACT

Underground cables are using widely as power networks expand, but they are also vulnerable to various faults caused by soil conditions, ageing, and damage by rodents. Locating the exact point of failure is challenging because the cable is buried and cannot be inspected visually. Without proper detection methods, large sections must be excavated, leading to unnecessary effort and cost. By identifying the precise location of the fault, only the affected portion of the cable needs to be accessed, which significantly reduces repair time and expenses. This project focuses on measuring the distance to a fault point from the control station in kilometres, enabling quicker maintenance of underground cable systems.

Keywords:- *Arduino, Transformer, Switches, LCD, Cables, Relay*

INTRODUCTION

This project presents a fault-location system for underground power cables using an Arduino based setup. The main objective is to measure the distance of a fault from the monitoring station in kilometres. The method is based on the principle of Ohm's law, where the change in resistance along the cable helps to determine the point at which a fault has occurred. When the cable develops a fault, the calculated distance is shown on the liquid crystal display (LCD).

Earlier, most power cables were installed overhead, but modern distribution networks increasingly use underground lines since they are unaffected by weather conditions such as storms, heavy rain, snow, and pollution. However, a major challenge with underground cables is identifying the exact fault location when a breakdown occurs, as the damaged section cannot be easily accessed. This project aims to overcome that difficulty by providing an accurate digital indication of the fault point, allowing repair teams to excavate only the affected section and reduce both time and effort.

Underground cabling is now common in many urban locations due to safety and reliability advantages, yet faults still occur due to ageing, moisture, mechanical damage, or insulation failure. Without knowing the precise fault point, repairs become complicated and time-consuming.

Cable faults are classified into two categories:

1. Open-circuit fault: In this condition, the current flow becomes zero because the conducting path is broken. The supply voltage appears at the output end. Although the system stops functioning, this type of fault is less harmful compared to short-circuit faults.

2. Short-circuit fault: Here, the

output voltage drops to zero while the current remains high. Short-circuit faults are further divided into:

The terminal method used in this project to detect the fault location by analyzing electrical parameters at the cable terminals. This method allows the fault point in underground cables to be identified with minimal manual effort.

It works by determining the fault type based on how the voltage drops along the length of cable as the current changes. A series of resistors are used to model the cable, and a DC supply is applied at one end. By monitoring the variation in voltage, the location of the fault can be identified. This helps technicians quickly trace the faulty section of the buried cable and speeds up the repair process.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Pavan Suresh Warade and Lakshman K. proposed a model for fault identification in underground cables using an 8051 microcontroller and IoT technology [1]. Their system measures changes in electrical parameters such as resistance and voltage to determine the fault distance from the monitoring point. An important feature of their design is the ability to transmit fault-related information to a web server in real time, allowing maintenance personnel to monitor cable conditions remotely and respond more quickly.

The authors also emphasized the low cost and scalability of their system, making it a practical solution for both rural and urban applications. Their work also opens possibilities for incorporating advanced sensors and predictive methods in future smart-grid developments.

Dr. G. Joga rao, S. Sharmilla, M. Mohan Avinash, N. Dileepkumar, S. Mohan swamy, and B. Ranjith Kumar studied

fault-distance analysis on underground cables [2]. They also developed a detection model using the 8051 microcontroller to identify faults and determine their distance from the base station.

Their method relies on tracking variations in line resistance and voltage to locate the fault point. Similar to earlier work, the authors integrated real-time data transmission, enabling quicker troubleshooting and reducing maintenance delays. Their approach reinforces the importance of microcontroller-based automation in improving power distribution reliability and supports the expansion of such systems into more advanced grid technologies.

Shaikh Shahir, Shaikh Tariq, Aqdas Bangi, and Khizar Khot introduced a GSM-based underground cable fault detection system using the AT89S52 microcontroller [3]. Their design continuously monitors the cable for abnormalities such as open circuits or short circuits by measuring voltage changes across different segments. When a fault is identified, the system calculates the approximate distance and sends an SMS alert to the concerned personnel through GSM communication.

This feature improves response time by providing immediate updates, reducing power outages and repair delays. The authors also discuss the cost-effectiveness and adaptability of their system, making it suitable for both existing and expanding cable networks, including those shifting toward smarter grid infrastructure.

R. K. Raghul Mansingh, R. Rajesh, S. Rama Subramani, and G. Ramkumar developed a method to detect high-impedance incipient faults in underground cables using a combination of Arduino and Raspberry Pi modules

[4]. These types of faults are often challenging to detect because they produce minimal current variations. Their system uses current transformers to continuously monitor the cable, with Arduino capturing sensor data and Raspberry Pi performing advanced processing.

This hybrid configuration improves sensitivity to small changes in current flow, making it possible to identify early-stage faults before they lead to severe cable damage or power interruptions. Their work highlights the importance of early fault detection and demonstrates how integrating multiple platforms can enhance system accuracy and performance.

METHODOLOGY

The proposed underground cable fault detection system operates on the principle of monitoring voltage variations across a simulated cable network to determine the location and nature of faults. The circuit uses an Arduino microcontroller as the central control unit, an LCD display for output, a relay section for switching, and a resistor network to represent different segments of the underground cable. The system is powered through a transformer, bridge rectifier, and filtering capacitor, which provide a stable DC supply for all components.

The methodology begins with the AC mains supply fed into a step-down transformer that outputs a low voltage AC signal. This AC supply is passed through a full-wave bridge rectifier, converting it to DC. A capacitor filter smooths the rectified output to ensure stable operation of the Arduino and associated electronics. This regulated power is delivered to the Arduino board, relays, and the LCD display module.

The Arduino reads voltage levels from three separate paths representing the three phases of an underground cable: R, Y, and B. These paths are created using a series of resistors connected in segments. Each segment represents an equal cable length, and the resistors simulate the resistance of real cable conductors. Switches located along each path act as fault points; when a switch is activated, it creates either an open-circuit or short-circuit fault depending on the configuration. These simulated faults cause a change in the voltage distribution across the resistor network.

Each phase is connected to the Arduino through analog input pins. Under normal conditions, the Arduino receives expected voltage values from the resistor ladder. When a fault occurs, the voltage at a specific analog input drops or rises significantly, indicating an abnormal condition.

The Arduino program interprets this voltage variation and calculates the approximate distance of the fault based on the corresponding resistor segment. For example, if the voltage changes at the third segment of the R-phase path, the microcontroller identifies that the fault lies near that section of the simulated cable.

Relays are included in the system to isolate the faulty phase if necessary. Each relay is driven by a transistor interfaced with the Arduino's digital output pins. When a fault is detected, the Arduino activates the respective relay to disconnect the affected line, preventing further damage. LEDs connected to the digital pins give visual indication of the operational status of each phase. A buzzer is also integrated to provide an audible alarm whenever a fault is detected.

The LCD display module, interfaced using I2C communication, shows real-time information such as phase status, fault presence, and the distance of the detected fault. This allows the user to quickly determine which line is affected and the approximate location of the fault.

Overall, the methodology combines electrical simulation, microcontroller-based measurement, and switching control to create a reliable underground cable fault detection model. By analyzing voltage variations across the simulated cable, the system accurately identifies both the phase and distance of the fault, enabling quick troubleshooting and reducing downtime in actual underground distribution networks.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

Fig.1:-Block Diagram

WORKING

The system starts with a 230 V AC supply, which is stepped down to 12 V by the transformer to ensure safe operating voltage for the electronics. This 12 V AC is fed into a bridge rectifier that converts it into pulsating DC. A capacitor filter smooths this DC output and provides a stable supply to

the Arduino Uno and other modules. The underground cable is represented using a series resistances, where each section corresponds to a particular length of cable. When a fault occurs either short circuit or open circuit the resistance value changes, causing a corresponding change in voltage across the cable model.

CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

Fig.2:-Circuit Diagram

This voltage variation is detected by the fault- location block, which identifies the affected section. The ULN2803 driver is used to amplify the control signals from the Arduino, enabling it to operate the relay module. The relays switch between different cable sections, allowing the Arduino to accurately determine the faulty phase and distance.

Once the Arduino processes the detected values, it displays the fault type and location on the LCD screen using the I2C interface. Simultaneously, a buzzer is activated to alert the user. This system enables quick and efficient identification of underground cable faults, improving maintenance response time.

ADVANTAGES

- The system requires minimal maintenance once installed.
- It offers better operational efficiency compared to traditional fault-finding methods.
- Underground cables experience fewer faults due to protection from external weather conditions and mechanical damage.
- The approach can be used for a wide range of cable voltages, from low-voltage 1 kV lines up to extra-high-voltage 500 kV networks.
- It is capable of identifying multiple types of cable faults, including short circuits, open circuits, resistive faults, insulation or sheath failures, moisture-related damage, and partial discharge issues.

FUTURE SCOPE

This project currently focuses on identifying the exact point of short-circuit faults in underground cables by measuring the distance from the feeder end using an Arduino. In future developments, the system can be expanded to work with AC circuits by incorporating capacitors to measure impedance changes. This enhancement would allow the model to identify open-circuit faults as well, making the system more versatile and suitable for a wider range of cable fault detection scenarios.

CONCLUSION

This project currently focuses on identifying the exact point of short-circuit faults in underground cables by measuring the distance from the feeder end using an Arduino. In future developments, the system can be expanded to work with AC circuits by incorporating capacitors to measure impedance changes. This enhancement would allow the model to identify open-circuit faults as well, making the system more versatile and suitable for a wider range of cable fault detection scenarios.

REFERENCES

1. Pavan Suresh Warade and Lakshman K, developed a system that focuses on designing and implementing an IoT-based method for identifying faults in underground power cables[1].
2. Dr. G. Joga rao, along with S Sharmilla, M. Mohan avinash, N. Dileep kumar, S. Mohan swamy and B. Ranjith kumar, carried out a study focused on analyzing techniques for locating the distance of short circuit faults in underground cables[2].
3. Shaikh shahir, Shaikh tariq, Aqdas bhangi and Khizar khot introduced a GSM-based underground cable fault detector system. Their approach sends automatic alerts to the operator when a fault occurs, enabling remote monitoring and quicker response. The system improves accessibility in areas where constant physical inspection is difficult, enhancing maintenance efficiency[3].
4. R. K. Raghul Mansingh, R. Rajesh, S. Rama Subramani and G. Ramkumar proposed a system that uses an Arduino controller to identify faults in underground cables. Their work explains how variations in electrical parameters help pinpoint the fault location, allowing faster maintenance and improving the reliability of cable networks[4]